

Mobile Teams: Reaching High-Risk Communities With Vaccination and Testing

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Background

- Efforts targeting marginalized groups are shown to decrease hospitalization and death
- Disproportionate effects from COVID-19 in Los Angeles County (LAC) were experienced due to inequitable social determinants of health (SDoH) and unequal vaccination
- The Mobile Vaccine Team (MVT) was created in 2021 to equitably distribute COVID-19 vaccines to affected communities

Problem

- Increased communicable disease (CD) in LAC
- Those most affected by CD, including COVID-19, tuberculosis, and STIs, have disproportionately high SDoH factors

Purpose

- To evaluate the use of a mobile team to address disparities in vaccination of high-risk communities
- A second aim was to evaluate the provision of communicable disease (CD) testing in high-risk settings

Social Determinants of Health

Conceptual Framework

PARiHS Model - Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services

Methods

- Quality improvement with evaluation of metrics
- Sample and Setting: Patients seen at mobile sites by MVT from July 26, 2023 – October 13, 2023
- Patients offered all services at vaccine or vaccine + testing sites
- Excel & Power BI data tracking of deidentified metrics; SPSS data analysis

Results

Testing Results	N	%
Negative	159	88.80%
Positive T-SPOT	6	3.40%
Invalid T-SPOT	2	1.10%
Borderline T-SPOT	1	0.60%
Positive Syphilis	8	4.50%
Positive Chlamydia	2	1.10%
Positive HIV and T-Spot	1	0.60%

Results

- 6048 vaccinated and 179 tested at 465 sites
- Over 10.5% positive
- 30% unable to disclose results due to loss to follow-up
- MVT has administered over 130,000 COVID-19 and 10,500 MPOX vaccines, plus many others

Conclusions

- Addressing negative SDoH, specifically access to health care and financial constraints, resulted in a significant increase in vaccinations and STI testing
- Access to at-risk populations gave the opportunity to provide additional services, such as Narcan and other harm reduction supplies
- Challenging follow-up as population was mainly persons experiencing homelessness (PEH) with no phone or internet access

Recommendations

- Continue vaccination and concurrent testing where feasible
- Add nurse practitioner for real-time treatment and follow-up of tests.
- Potential for additional team members such as social worker
- For future projects, offer additional testing for Hepatitis B and C, Trichomonas, and pregnancy

References

